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COMPLEX SYSTEMS INTEGRATION USING CLOUD-BASED SERVICES

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Abstract: Cloud-based IT services have become an integral part of modern businesses. One such service is Function as a Service (FaaS), which is a cloud-based microservice. This paper focuses on cloud-based microservices and their ability to integrate complex systems. A pilot project is presented to demonstrate the practicality of using cloud-based microservices in various application domains and business models that involve interactions among humans, machines, environments, and other responsive components. The results of this study show that cloud-based microservices can be used to create scalable and efficient systems that can handle complex interactions.

Keywords: microservices architecture, cloud computing, complex system, function as a service, system integration

I. INTRODUCTION

Microservices is a software architecture style that allows applications to be built through loosely coupled, fine-grained small services [1]. Communications among microservices are through light-weight APIs [2]. Microservices are self-contained, independent deployment modules. The cost of scaling is comparatively less than the monolithic architecture. Microservices are independently manageable with minimal impact on existing services, and scale as need arise [3]. Furthermore, they work well with agile development processes and satisfy the increasing need for a more fluid flow of information. Due to such advantages, microservices have become a go-to architectural style over the traditional monolithic architectural styles. More and more businesses and applications are revolutionizing their IT solutions through adopting microservices [4]. They offer simpler solutions for enterprise-grade apps, as they often utilize smaller code bases; thereby being easier to track, understand, keep clean,

troubleshoot, update, and manage for developers. Since they are also independently deployable, enabling continuous improvement and faster app updates, they allow for more team autonomy. However, as we build more complex systems, which are often heterogeneous, hybrid, responsive, intelligent, and environmentally integrated, integration of Microservice driven architectures becomes a major issue. The functioning of these systems depends on the interactions of components belonging to different domains, built on different platforms, and following different rules and protocols. Thus, it is a challenging task to integrate these components seamlessly to provide the customers with a dependable product or a satisfactory service.

Hence in this paper, we describe cloud-based microservices and their potential usage to integrate complex systems. A pilot project is built to evaluate this idea. Specifically, Microsoft Azure-based microservices are utilized to integrate the complex systems and they are demonstrated to be effective and manageable solutions.

The remaining of this paper is organized as the following. In Section II, various complex systems are described. In Section III, microservices, especially cloud-based microservices are described. In Section IV, a pilot project using cloud-based microservices to integrate complex systems is described. Conclusions are given in Section V.

II. COMPLEX SYSTEMS

In this paper, the term “complex system” is used to describe any system that involves components of different domains, built on different platforms, and serving different needs. There are many types of complex systems, each of which has its own properties. We here describe some common properties that are often seen in these complex systems. It is worth noting that a complex system does not need to have all these properties. If they share one or more of these properties, they are considered as a complex system.

A. Heterogeneous

A complex system might have components from different domains. These components could be built with different infrastructure and on different platforms. They might follow different rules and have different communication protocols [6]. For example, a distributed computing system built with various public resources is a heterogeneous complex system, because the public computing resource may include workstations, personal computers, and tablets, running different operating systems. Project SETI@Home is such an example [7].

B. Hybrid

A hybrid system is a complex system that consists of both analog and digital parts [8]. When a control system is hybrid, the signals could be time-driven, which is continuous, or event-driven, which is discrete. Traffic control is an example of a hybrid system, where traffic flow is continuously collected and monitored, and traffic incidents are considered discrete events. The use of hybrid systems that process both continuous and discrete input data in traffic control has become increasingly popular in recent years. For example, an intelligent traffic control system based on wireless sensor networks (WSNs) has been proposed to collect data on road traffic and available parking spaces in smart cities. The system integrates three smart subsystems connected to each other (crossroad management, parking space management, and a mobile application) to connect citizens to a smart city.

C. Human-Machine Interaction

A complex system often requires the interactions between a human and a machine. The human role includes not only the direct manual control of elementary processes, but also the complex decision making [9]. For example, a digital insurance brokerage could be considered as a human-machine system, where customers fill the applications online and the machine (computers) could validate their identity, look up their traffic violation history, and determine the premiums. The result should be

examined, and the final decisions should be made by a human being to avoid possible machine errors.

D. Intelligent

A complex system could be built with artificial intelligent components to help it make a better decision. For example, big data analysis using machine learning technology could be built into a product recommendation system for an online retailer. The system could make real-time product recommendations based on user’s shopping record, browsing history, and market trend [10].

E. Environment Interacted

Some applications often require the system to collect, analyze, and respond to the data collected from its surrounding environment. The environment factors could be natural, such as temperature, light, precipitation, wind, chemicals, and radiation. They could also be human-related, such as heartbeat, vehicle speed, room occupancy, and traffic flow. Embedded systems are commonly used in these applications. Internet of Things (IoT) belongs to this category [11].

A system with one of the above five properties is considered complex. Modern applications usually involve complex components with more than one of these five properties. We accordingly need a cross-platform, cross-domain, and lightweight mechanism to integrate a complex system.

III. CLOUD-BASED MICROSERVICES

Traditional IT services are built in the monolithic style, where infrastructure, platforms, applications, and storage are all integrated in one system. Microservice, on the other side, is a software architecture style that allows applications to be built through loosely coupled, fine-grained small services. Compared with monolithic systems, microservices have the following advantages [12].

- Reusable. Each individual service is easy to reuse in other applications.
- Scalable. Because of loose coupling, scaling up and down the services have minimum effects on other services.
- Small code base, which reduces the complexity of development and testing.
- Less deployment and restart time.

Another important property of microservices is that their communications are done through light-weighted APIs, allowing them to be used right out the box with little to no integration overhead [13]. Therefore, microservices are great choices for complex system integration.

Cloud-based microservices are specifically developed to run on the cloud, which make the services more distributed and independent. In addition, cloud computing platforms can provide Function as a Service (FaaS), which is both serverless and cost effective [14]. Figure 1 compares

monolithic application, microservices, and Function as a Service (FaaS).

FaaS is a key component of a data mesh architecture as it enables the development of domain-specific data products that can be deployed to the data mesh. By using FaaS, developers can focus on building the business logic of their data products, while the underlying infrastructure is managed by the cloud provider. The following FaaS properties make it appealing for adoption for complex and large-scale systems development.

- Customers are responsible only for maintaining their function code, while the cloud service provider hosts and manages the entire back-end operation.
- Customers only pay for the actual runtime required to execute the function, which may take a fraction of a second. There is no other overhead charge.
- Most cloud service providers do not charge for storing the function on the cloud.
- These functions are usually short, less complex, and easy to maintain.
- These functions are stored on cloud with simple interface, making them accessible to various applications across different platforms.

Figure 1: Comparisons of monolithic application, microservices, and function as a service.

These properties show that FaaS is technically manageable and economically competitive. Therefore, FaaS is gaining adoption rate across various applications, such as data processing, validation, and mobile and IoT applications [15]. Popular FaaS includes Microsoft’s Azure Function, Amazon’s AWS Lambda Function, and Google’s Cloud Function [16] [17].

IV. INTEGRATING COMPLEX SYSTEMS WITH CLOUD-BASED MICROSERVICES

A. System Description

We built a pilot project called **Automobile Service System**. This system contains six major components: an automobile (car, truck, SUV, etc.), a service center, a service scheduler, distributed service teams, a service log database, and the billing department. The system is considered hybrid, heterogeneous, and intelligent, with human interactions as shown below.

Figure 2 illustrates the six components. The **Automobile** has an embedded computer system with sensors to accept analog data, such as engine speed, temperature, time pressure, etc. Therefore, it is a hybrid system. On the other side, it is also intelligent with an event driven (such as accident) monitoring system. In addition, it is connected to the Internet using Internet of Things (IoT) technology. If an abnormal signal is detected, a warning message needs to be sent to the service center to request a service.

The **Service Center** maintains a list of service requests. The list is updated in real-time. The **Service Scheduler** is a computer program that uses artificial intelligence to better match the service request with a nearby service team.

Figure 2: Six components of the Automobile Service System.

When the **Service Team** receives the service task, including automobile location, they will visit the customer and make the reparations. After the service is done, its status is updated, and the service record will be saved in the **Service Log**. After a complete service is recorded in the service log, the **Billing Department** will be notified to send the service bill to the customer.

B. Integration

To integrate this system, we use Azure Functions, which are cloud-based microservices provided by Microsoft. The solution to this **Automobile Service System** is illustrated in Figure 3. The four Azure functions are described below.

F1 is an **HTTP Trigger Function**. When it receives an HTTP request from the automobile, it forwards the request to the Service Center. The Service Center is implemented with Azure Blob, which stores the request. The reason Azure Blob is used here is that any kind of data can be stored in Blob and every message is assigned a URL and can be accessed through HTTP protocol.

F2 is a **Blob Trigger Function**. After a new item (service request) is inserted into the blob, the request will be forwarded to the Service Scheduler. The Service Scheduler maintains the service request with Azure Queue. Just like the regular data structure queue, Azure Queue schedules tasks following FIFO (first in, first out) order. When a new request arrives, it is inserted into the queue,

when the request is assigned to a service team, it is removed from the queue.

F3 is an **Azure Durable Function**. Azure durable function is stateful and it can pause and wait for user input. **F3** has two parts: **D1** and **D2**. **D1** implements an HTTP method (get or post) that awaits the scheduling message from the Service Scheduler. Once Function **D1** is invoked, it forwards the service task to the service team through email or text message. At this moment, **F3** is paused in sleep mode. After the service task is completed, say, days later, the service team needs to awake **F3** through invoking an HTTP method to continue the execution of **D2**. **D2** will write the service record in the Service Log, which is implemented with Azure Cosmos DB, a NoSQL database. The reason a NoSQL database is used here is that any information regarding the service can be recorded. There is field limit given by a relational database.

F4 is a Cosmos DB trigger function. Once a new service record is created, **F4** will be invoked to send the completed service information to the Billing Department.

Figure3: Integration of the Automobile Service Systems with Azure Functions.

C. Summary

This simple pilot project is a typical representation of a complex system made up of heterogeneous, hybrid, and intelligent components. It also involves human interaction. The automobile's sensors are also integrated with its internal environment. Therefore, this project contains all the necessary properties of a complex system.

The Azure Functions used to integrate the system are easy to program. They are stored on the cloud, making them easy to maintain and reuse. Their "Pay As You Go" mode also makes them cost effective.

It is worth noting that if the components in the project are implemented by a different vendor using different technologies, we need to rewrite the Azure Functions. In other words, these Azure functions should be customized to the specific application.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper described cloud-based microservices, especially Function as a Service (FaaS). A pilot project is presented to illustrate the feasibility of using cloud-based microservices to integrate complex systems.

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